

Assessment of Awareness Regarding Diabetic Retinopathy among Diabetes Mellitus Patients at a Tertiary Care CenterJemi Sandhyavali Lam¹, Harika Mada², Sai Pavan Kalyan Dasari³¹Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, GGH, Guntur²Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, GGH, Guntur³Post Graduate, Department of Ophthalmology, GGH, Guntur

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Abstract:

Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a common complication of diabetes and a leading cause of blindness globally. Early detection and timely management are crucial to prevent vision loss. The study was conducted during a six-month period from October 2023 to March 2024 and it evaluates the awareness of diabetic retinopathy among diabetic patients visiting Government general hospital, Guntur. We have done interviews to evaluate knowledge level and attitude of patient's towards eye care. A total of 200 patients were included of which 94 were males and 106 females. 79% of the participants were unaware of visual complications of diabetes. 78.5% of patients believed adequate glycemic control could prevent any diabetes related visual complications and only 12% were aware of the treatment options available for diabetic retinopathy. The results indicated a significant proportion of patients lacked sufficient knowledge about the risks, symptoms, and preventive measures of diabetic retinopathy. This highlights the need for targeted educational programs and improved screening protocols to enhance early detection and appropriate management of diabetic retinopathy, thus reducing the burden of visual impairment among diabetics.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus, Diabetic retinopathy, Awareness.

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus, the most common endocrine disease in the world, is characterized by hyperglycaemia, which causes various microvascular and neurological disorders.[1] Diabetic retinopathy has become a leading cause of vision impairment leading to irreversible blindness in adults. It generally begins as a neuro-retinopathy with subsequent vascular changes occurring later as a result of a breakdown of the blood-retinal barrier and occlusion of retinal capillaries.[2] Uncontrolled blood sugar levels, age, long-term diabetes, high blood pressure, smoking, and high cholesterol are some of the risk factors that worsen DR complications.[3] In a study done by Teo et.al revealed that among people with diabetes, the global prevalence was 22.27% for diabetic retinopathy, 6.17% for VTDR (vision-threatening diabetic retinopathy), and 4.07% for CSME (clinically significant macular oedema).[4] If left untreated, diabetic retinopathy can lead to severe, irreversible vision loss. Therefore prompt detection and treatment of diabetic retinopathy plays a key role in preserving vision.[5] Increasing awareness of eye screening to detect diabetic retinopathy changes is an important

factor in its management.[6] Increasing knowledge among diabetic patients may help change their attitude toward early eye examinations and regular visits to their diabetic care providers. This helps in better management of diabetes and its ocular comorbidities which, in turn, prevent diabetic retinopathy-related vision loss.[7] This study was intended to survey the awareness of diabetic retinopathy among patients with diabetes and its complications as it helps in seeking timely and appropriate intervention.

Materials and Methods

The aim of the study is to assess the awareness regarding diabetic retinopathy among diabetes mellitus patients visiting OPD of Department of General Medicine and Department of Ophthalmology in GGH, Guntur. It is a cross sectional and observational study. The study was conducted over a six-month period from October 2023 to March 2024 with a sample size of 200. Patients with diabetes, aged >18 years and who are willing to give informed consent were included in the study. Patients not willing to give consent were not included. A pre-designed questionnaire in local language was used for data collection which contained infor-

mation about demographic details, effects of diabetes on the eyes, frequency of retinal evaluation, and duration of diabetes mellitus. Consent was taken from each participant. The questionnaire included the following questions shown in table 1.

The institutional ethics clearance was taken from the ethics committee before the start of the study, and informed consent was taken from every participant. The certificate number is

Results

A total of 200 patients were included in the study, of which 94 were male and 106 were female. The mean age of the study group was 57.9 years, ranging from 38 years to 93 years. Among 200 patients, 124 were in the 38 - 60year age group and 76 people belonged to >60year age group. Majority of the participants are from rural areas (168 patients) while some from urban areas (42 patients). Duration of diabetes ranged from 1-5 years in 86 participants, 5-10 years in 60 and >10 years in 25 participants. A total of 164 patients were taking oral hypoglycaemic agents, 31 were on both insulin and oral medication and only 1 patient was using insulin alone, 4 were recently diagnosed and not currently on any medication for diabetes.

Regarding the educational qualification of participants, out of 200, 24 studied up to 10th standard, 6 people held a degree and remaining 170 participants were uneducated.

Data obtained showed that 42 people were aware diabetes could cause visual disturbances while 158 were unaware. 34 participants were aware of the relation between diabetes and retinal vascular changes associated with it. 30 were aware of Diabetic Retinopathy while 170 people were unaware. This data is shown in figure 1.

A total of 157 participants believed adequate blood sugar control could prevent diabetes related vision

problems and only 59 participants in the study group thought taking appropriate spectacle correction will be enough to treat diabetes related visual problems. This is shown in figure 2. In our study the main reason for not getting a regular eye check-up is due to lack of knowledge of diabetic retinopathy. This is seen in a total of 113 patients. Other reasons include no vision problem (49), living in a remote area (18) and having adequate blood sugar control (20). It is depicted in figure 3. Majority of the participants (142) didn't know about the frequency of eye check-up needed after a diagnosis with diabetes mellitus, 23 believed a follow up every 6 months was needed while 35 thought 1 year follow up interval was needed.

Regarding the duration between the diagnosis of diabetes and development of retinal vascular changes, 11 thought retinal vascular changes could develop 6 months after diagnosis of diabetes, 53 thought it would be seen 1 year after diagnosis and 44 participants thought it would take >2 years for the changes to take place after diagnosis with diabetes, the rest 92 participants didn't know when the changes would appear. Almost all the participants, 198 were unaware to the fact that diabetic retinopathy changes could be present at the time of diagnosis with diabetes mellitus, only 2 people agreed as shown in figure4. The entire study group followed a sedentary life style with everyone (200) not participating in any exercise or activities.

With respect to treatment, 24 participants knew diabetic retinopathy is treatable while 176 participants didn't know treatment could reduce diabetic retinopathy. Among 200, 7 participants were aware of laser treatment, 19 were aware of Intravitreal injections while 45 others thought oral medication could treat diabetic retinopathy, the remaining 129 participants weren't aware of any treatment to diabetic retinopathy as described in figure 5.

Figure 1: bar diagrams showing awareness among diabetics regarding visual disturbances, its relation with retinal vascular changes and about diabetic retinopathy

Figure 2: bar diagrams showing the knowledge of patients to treat diabetes related visual problems

Figure 3: pie diagram showing reason for not getting eye check-up, and most common being lack of knowledge of DR

Figure 4: showing awareness of patients regarding development of retinal changes after diagnosis of diabetes and frequency of eye checkups

Figure 5: bar diagram showing various treatment methods and the number of participants aware of it

Table 1: shows a predesigned questionnaire used in this study.

Table 1- Questionnaire given to all patients	
1.	Duration of diabetes? (1-5 yrs/5-10 yrs/>10 yrs)
2.	Do you think there is a relationship between diabetes and diabetic retinopathy? (Yes/No)
3.	Do you exercise regularly? (Yes/No)
4.	Duration of treatment for diabetes? (1-5 yrs/5-10 yrs/>10 yrs)
5.	Type of medication used for diabetes? (Oral meds/Insulin/Both)
6.	Do you think diabetes can lead to blindness? (Yes/No)
7.	Do you think retinal vascular changes can be present at the time of diagnosis with diabetes? (Yes/No)
8.	Do you know the frequency of eye checkup needed after diagnosis with diabetes? (6 mo/1 yr/No)
9.	Do you think getting a spectacle prescription is enough to treat diabetes related visual problems? (Yes/No)
10.	Do you think adequate blood sugar control can prevent diabetic retinopathy? (Yes/No)
11.	Do you know diabetic retinopathy can be treated? (Yes/No)
12.	Reason for not getting an eye checkup?
13.	Are you aware about diabetic retinopathy? (Yes/No)
14.	When do you think diabetic retinopathy manifests after diagnosis with diabetes? (6 mo/1 yr/>2 yr)
15.	Educational qualification (Uneducated/Upto 10th standard/Degree)
16.	Current residing area? (Rural/Urban)
17.	Are any of your family members suffering with diabetes related visual disturbances? (Yes/No)
18.	Do you know about treatment options for diabetic retinopathy? (Oral meds/Intravitreal inj/Laser)

Discussion

Lack of awareness about diabetic retinopathy is a major health issue as it leads to progression of the condition resulting in irreversible vision loss.

In Our study, 21% of patients were aware that diabetes can affect the eye. About 56.5% of the study participants didn't undergo an eye check-up being unaware about diabetic retinopathy, 24.5% of patients stated no problem with vision as the reason for not undergoing an eye check-up, 9% of the people mentioned living in a remote area as being a factor and 10% revealed having an adequate blood sugar control as the reason. This is very important as most of the participants are from rural background, thus, indicating a need to bring more awareness about diabetes and its complications. Among men and women, men are relatively more aware of diabetic retinopathy changes than women,

therefore it is very important to create awareness of the condition among women as their awareness helps to motivate all other family members to undergo regular eye check-ups.

In the current study, 78.5% of participants felt adequate blood sugar control could prevent diabetes related visual disturbances, irrespective of their knowledge about diabetic retinopathy.

71% of the study participants didn't have knowledge about the frequency of eye check-ups needed after diagnosis of diabetes, 11.5% believed a 6 monthly follow up was needed and 17.5% believed 1 yearly follow up was needed. This shows that patients with diabetes are not aware of the frequency of eye check-ups needed. Physicians play a crucial role to counsel patients regarding screening for diabetic retinopathy in all newly diagnosed diabetics and refer to ophthalmologist

for fundus examination and follow up with atleast one annual check-up thereafter. This helps in at least reducing the burden of visual impairment.

Patients should not wait till visual deterioration occurs. Depending on availability of resources visual acuity testing, retinal examination and fundus imaging can be readily performed in diabetic patients in primary care.

Early detection and timely treatment, such as laser therapy or injections, can significantly slow or prevent vision loss. This highlights the importance of integrating regular eye check-ups into diabetes management plans.

Facilities like remote retinal imaging should be increased in rural areas. A team of ophthalmologists, general physicians and health care educators are essential to enhance awareness about DR.

Conclusion

Overall In our study we have seen that there is a critical gap in awareness regarding diabetic retinopathy, particularly among diabetic patients. This lack of awareness among patients about the risks, symptoms, and preventive measures associated with diabetic retinopathy necessitates the need for targeted educational initiatives to improve knowledge among patients.

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